

Summary NASA-CERN Open Science Summit 2023

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Day 1: 10th of July

Panel Discussion: Developing Open Science Policies

Moderator:

Chris Bourg (MIT Libraries)

Panelists:

Arianna Becerril-García (Redalyc)

Ana Persic (UNESCO)

Opening statements

Arianna Becerril-García:

- Open science is not an end in itself, but a means to achieve science as a global public good
- The goal of open science practices should be to achieve a transition from science as a commodity to science as a global public good
- Systemic and structural open science for the common good needs to affect change on various levels: research practice, infrastructure, cultural disruption, policy
- Commercial approaches to open science can lead to patronizing strategies; for instance, waiver fees in open access publishing
- What do we lose by allowing science to enter the logic of the market? -> Institutional infrastructure, sustainability, control and the capacity to take decisions, publishing tradition that perpetuates the non-commercial sector
- **Non-commercial open science is the closest path toward realizing science as a public good !!!**

Ana Persic:

- Why open science? -> Increased access to knowledge, improved quality, control and sustainability
- How to do open science? Infrastructures, incentives, capacities, policy (everything needs to be tackled in parallel)
- Why open science policy?: Show commitment, build stability, enhance clarity, engage affected actors and remove barriers
- International policy framework on open science: democratize the entire scientific process -> see Unesco recommendations for open science

Discussion

What are important areas of inquiry right now in the context of open science?

How to coordinate open science efforts across different contexts and stay true to the values of open science (Arianna Becerril-García)

Approaching open science in innovative ways. For instance, creating new collaborations through open science (especially between the global south and north) and asking how to give visibility to less recognized knowledge systems in order to enhance equitable participation in research (Ana Persic)

How much cultural change (in beforehand) has to take place till a policy can be effective?

Transversal disruptions need to occur. Researchers have to see their career from a different perspective. This needs to happen simultaneously with changes in policy (Arianna Becerril-García)

Everything needs to happen at once. During the process, it is crucial that investments in science are not reduced. There can not be two (funding) tracks (one for science, one for open science). Don't think about open science as taking money from other parts of science, but rather as part of a general investment in science (Ana Persic)

What are some of the unanswered questions regarding the current state of open science?

What innovations are required to achieve the societal goals set forth by Unesco? How can knowledge from the global south be better represented? (Ana Persic)

How might research produced in the global south be dispersed more successfully? How can the sometimes-contradictory policies of different organizations work successfully together? (Ariana Becerril-Garca)

Importance of Infrastructure: Could unesco play a role in building platforms that make all open resources available globally (instead of national infrastructures)?

Would have to be a collective endeavor (of laboratories and national contexts) (Ana Persic)

Are there different ends that actors pursue with open science practices?

There are different perspectives, but they should be communicated to develop common goals and a ecology of connected infrastructures (Arianna Becerril-García)

Which policies should exist in the future? Who should be making/maintaining policies?

There are various policy development strategies that can work:

- Policies on different elements of open science (works in some instances), in some cases these are too fragmented
- General national policy that institutions can adopt

- Integration of openness into existing policy systems (particularly in southern countries) (Ana Persic)

Policies as ways of making concrete commitments (Arianna Becerril-García)

How can we engage researchers to get continuous feedback from them?

Outline how knowledge production processes of researchers can be improved by open science practices (Arianna Becerril-García)

What is the scope of open science (only addressing natural sciences or also social sciences)?

Open science refers to all sciences (Arianna Becerril-García, Ana Persic)

Key takeaways

- The panel addressed the general relevance of open science policies: Policies are necessary to show commitment, build stability, enhance clarity and remove barriers in the practice of open science.
- The panel stressed the need to focus on the goals of open science in developing open science policies: Open science should not be an end in itself, but a means to achieve science as a global public good.
- The panel further underscored that the introduction of open science policies needs to be accompanied by various other elements, such as the development of infrastructures for the release of open science resources, an incentive structure that credits open science practices and a general cultural shift in the research practices of many scientists.
- Additionally, a criticism towards economic open science models was formulated: By allowing open science to enter the logic of the market, institutions risk their capacity to take independent action and sustain their open science endeavors in the long run. The panel thus stressed that non-commercial open science is the best path towards realizing science as a public good.
- Further, a key challenge to be addressed in the context of open science policy development was formulated: It is still not entirely clear how we can advance epistemic justice through practicing open science. We need to develop ways in which we can make particular types of knowledge visible through open science practice.

Panel Discussion: Analysis of Open Science Policies

Moderator:

Greg Tananbaum (Open Research Funders Group)

Panelists:

Michael Arentoft (European Commission)

Josh Greenberg (Alfred P. Sloan Foundation)

Bob Hanish (NIST)

Heather Joseph (SPARC)

Nokuthula Mchunu (NRF South Africa)

Brian Nosek (Center for Open Science)

Opening statements

Michael Arentoft:

- We don't need open science policy, we need science policy which values openness: Science is intrinsically open
- There is still many issues regarding openness in contemporary scientific research: There is a lack in open access to publications and data, in particularly FAIR data, due to a missing of recognition of open science practices

Josh Greenberg:

- Science is a socio-technical system. No solely technical or social solution will enable the implementation of open science: strategies need to address both aspects

Bob Hanish:

- It's important not to increase the burden to make data open through policies: it's essential to be cautious in formulating policy requirements

Heather Joseph:

- Open science and knowledge sharing are a human right

Nokuthula Mchunu:

- The objective of open science should be to increase the contribution of science to society through knowledge creation. Instead of focusing on how to organize academic communication, the question is how to turn science into a global public

good.

Brian Nosek:

- To realize open science, you need to coordinate policy, practice and infrastructure. This is a very difficult undertaking.

Discussion

What does it mean to advance a culture of open science?

Show how open science will advance the generation of public good
Break down open science to the individual (what can researchers do specifically)
(Heather Joseph)

Establish reward systems that acknowledge open science contributions (Nokuthula Mchunu)

Institutional policies don't necessarily affect individual behavior, there needs to be reward systems that affect individuals (Brian Nosek)

Respect different institutional commitments, develop infrastructures for rewarding researchers and implementing open science (Michael Arentoft)

Different levels that affect change: Individuals, institutions, technology/infrastructure (Josh Greenberg)

Small culture change is the beginning (e.g., data sharing within an institution between two researchers) (Bob Hanish)

How to break out of stagnation/the feeling that you can't do anything as an individual?

Removing journal impact factor as assessment and think about alternative metrics and responsible use of quantitative indicators (Michael Arentoft)

"Misidentified dependencies": Feeling that somebody else has to do something before you take action -> show how individuals can take immediate action (Josh Greenberg)

Incremental change: one early adopter can make all the difference (Bob Hanish)

Can we make it a competitive advantage to be an early adopter in open science? -> alternative metrics (Heather Joseph)

Don't think that approaches need to be perfect, often projects emerge out of trial and error procedures. (Nokuthula Mchunu)

What are the specific changes we need to implement in the scientific reward structure to meaningfully incentivize open data, open source, reproducibility, and the other key topics of this Summit?

Development of new metrics: e.g., around data use (Josh Greenberg, Nokuthula Mchunu)

Move away from counting publications, ask what the intellectual contribution of an individual is (Bob Hanish)

Individual performance assessment is dominant in contemporary scientific practice, find ways to evaluate collaborative research (Heather Joseph)

Think about reward systems for institutions and how to transform them (Brian Nosek)

Create coherence within different reward systems, revise structures and increase funding (Michael Arentoft)

Enable the participation of early career researchers in research assessment (Heather Joseph)

Current issue in Europe: How to ensure Interoperability of data standards?

Debate in which instances interoperability makes sense, sometimes it's not realistic or practical (Bob Hanish)

Think about modular approach to standards, pick the ones that work for specific institutions (Brian Nosek)

Only connect standards when necessary (Michael Arentoft)

How do we change bad incentives from funders?

DORA, CoARA initiatives show how some funders are interested in changing research assessment (Michael Arentoft)

Establish citation practices for diverse resources -> show how open data creates further value

Establish metadata quality measurements (e.g., is there uncertainty information attached to data?) (Bob Hanish)

What are incentives for leaders of research organizations to implement open science?

Show how open science can help tackle societal challenges. (Greg Tananbaum)

Open science as a way to generate a societal impact (Nokuthula Mchunu)

Open science as improving the efficiency and interdisciplinarity of research (Michael Arentoft)

Role of commercial publishers? What would be their role in reward systems that reward open science?

It's necessary to debate what functions institutions are willing to grant to financial players (Heather Joseph)

We should discuss what are/should be the costs of publishing (Nokuthula Mchunu)

It's essential to debate what role universities could play in publishing

Should we only refer to researchers (or also infrastructure maintainers, IT staff ect.) ?

We should think about the language here -> who do we want to refer to? -> Maybe researchers is not inclusive enough

Key takeaways

- Similar to the previous session, the panelists of this session argued that open science policy developers should focus on the larger goals connected to open science practice, such as the tackling of societal challenges.
- Additionally, there was a longer discussion on the establishment of reward systems that acknowledge the relevance of open science practices. Panelists have argued that it should become a competitive advantage to be an early adopter of open science practices. This could be achieved through the establishment of reward systems that move away from counting publications towards the development of alternative metrics and a qualitative assessment of the intellectual contributions of individuals.
- The panelists additionally discussed how leaders of research organizations could be convinced to adopt open science practices. Here, it is crucial to demonstrate how open science is capable of tackling societal challenges and improving the efficiency and interdisciplinarity of research.

- Throughout the discussion, the panelists stressed that the goal of policies should not be the establishment of perfect open science practices: It is important to test out what works through a trial and error approach.

Clinics summary: Strategic Plans and Policies

Assessing Existing Policies

Policy needs to be abstract enough to address the needs of different disciplines/ departments ect., while still providing concrete pathways and examples.

Policy -> implementation needs:

- policy
- guidance/pathways
- accountability/social contract

Highlight example of Accountability/Social Contract:

- Review Period
- Implementers as reviewers of each other

Gap to address:

- Policy as support for researcher decision-making
- Policy for sustainability

Creating a Policy Resource

- Website that aggregates access to open science policies (create search engine that enables selection based on particular institutional requirements)
- Catalog and option list for definitions
- Discuss the scope for data that needs to be made public
- Comment from the audience: build a community around it?
- Support to build and maintain these resources

Strategic Action Plan Development Group A

Understanding?

- Strategic Action Plan vs Policy? -> Strategic Plans can Lead to Policy
- Before or after policy? -> depends
- Connect it to the value and mission of an institution!!

Leadership:

- Government in terms of funding: Can have data on allocation
- Lead or part of the movement?
- Argue how open science can address the missions of an organization
- Encouraging language “like support and engage”
- Influence in Policy internal ..globally

Community:

- Find champions
- Determine stakeholders on the policy decision
- Define good practices
- Find partners

Metrics

- Adopt
- Move forward to encourage
- Indicate open on OA or OD as examples
- Example metrics and how ?
- Community communication

Strategic Action Plan Development Group B

General Approach

Strategy vs policy; which comes first? How formal should the plan be?

Resource: catalog of common roadblocks and how to bypass

Defining roles and responsibilities for implementation

Communication & Gaining Support

Nomenclature; use of “open” won’t always help

Framing as a means to achieve organizational goals for science, not open science as the end goal

Leadership and community buy in; how much consultation?

Values & Incentives

Values differ for institution vs researcher/developer

Opportunities for tenure/promotion evaluation

Strategic Action Plan Development Group C

Difference between strategy and policy (can have the former without the latter?)

Potential levers for action:

- Compare with peer activities, inspire FOMO
- Mobilize researchers, mobilize funders

- Standardization (of metadata, tooling, machine readability) costs, pricing, and economic factors
- Computing architecture (move to the cloud)
- Pressures on boundaries of org mission (commercial, international)
- 3rd-party funding for pilots to demonstrate demand
- Coordinated efforts like

Examples: Data Management Plans, FAIR

Strategic Action Plan Development Group D

- In the action plan, you need clear definitions of roles and responsibilities.
- It does not need to cover all areas of open science but can refer to a general policy as a source of legitimacy.
- Before publishing an action plan, support and services must be in place. E.g. creating an OSPO, data stewards/curators, process definition/certification, tools and training.
- An intermediate layer is needed between high-management and practitioners.
- Look at legal frameworks of regions, countries, etc. before you start defining the action plan.
- Open sourcing everything is not an optimal strategy. We need to define guidelines and processes on how to define what to open source to make sure there is added value given the resources.
- Open science support teams should partner with Tech Transfer offices to avoid incompatible mandates inside an organisation.
- Define roles and borders of responsibility in public/private partnerships.
- Action plan submitted to regular updates.

Open Science Policy Development

Key issues surfaced:

Current policies are very vague. We need concrete policies showing the value of the policy for each actor.

- Tailored narratives for each type of actor/user to increase policy engagement.
- People with expertise on the matter within teams to facilitate implementation.

Resources that would help (e.g., topics or examples for a policymakers' toolkit):

- Beyond toolkits we need actionable documents on procedures and how to support operations and daily decision making

Winning strategies that were identified:

- Identify your local champions.
- Participating in events like this one exchanging knowledge

OpenAIRE Policy Workshop A

- Policies mean different things to different organizations / contexts (from vision to roadmaps and rules)
- Understand the legal, standards and ethical context before producing a new policy
- Focus and understand who writes and who reads the policy
- Do not reinvent the wheel: (re)use a policy someone else has created
- Open Science is essential for good science (reproducible/ sustainable/ community engaging)
- Do not call everything open science: if you wish to do open data, do open data)
- Have different communities talking to each other
- Maximise value from the Open Science stack, by being tactical (quick wins) and strategic (long term vision)

Key takeaways

- The clinic on “assessing existing policies” suggested that future open science policies should focus on the development of strategies that guarantee the sustainability of open science practices and that provide support for researchers in taking concrete decisions throughout the research process.
- The clinic on “creating a policy resource” suggested strategies for pooling existing knowledge on policy development, for instance through the creation of a website that aggregates open science policies and makes them searchable.
- The clinic on “Open Science Policy Development” stressed that it is necessary to develop policies that provide tailored narratives for practitioners to increase policy engagement.
- The “OpenAIRE Policy” clinic asserted that it is essential to understand the legal and ethical context of a research field before introducing a new policy.
- The clinics that focused on “strategic action plan development” asserted that it is crucial to align the vision articulated in an action plan with the mission of an organization. The clinics further suggested that it is important to connect to the research community addressed through a strategic action plan. This is for instance possible by advocating the use of alternative metrics that credit open science contributions.

Day 2: 11th of July

Panel Discussion: Open Data in Practice

Moderator:

Daniel Spichtinger

Speakers:

Chelle Gentemann (NASA)

Sarah Jones (EOSC)

Kati Lassila-Perini (Helsinki Institute of Physics/CMS Collaboration)

Tibor Simko (CERN)

Opening statements

Chelle Gentemann:

- NASA needs to develop strategies for releasing data in the petabyte region: there is a large amount of data that has not been analyzed yet and could be made openly accessible for further (re)use
- Recent updates of the scientific information policy at NASA: Peer-reviewed publications are made openly available with no embargo period; research data and software are shared at the time of publication or the end of the funding award; mission data is released as soon as possible and unrestricted mission software is developed openly; Science workshops and meetings are held openly to enable broad participation
- Infrastructure for open data release at NASA: Science explorer

Sarah Jones:

- Data management is a concern that naturally arises from routine research practice and is essential for open data efforts: Data cannot be made open and FAIR if it is not maintained properly.
- The creation of commons, such as open data spaces, requires some fundamental components: 1. human and governance aspects (white) 2. technical and content elements (blue) 3. interoperability (dark blue,) "the core glue"
- The problem is NOT Open Data, it's interoperability!
- We need an open API layer, series of protocols, standards, schemas, crosswalks... etc
- Allow data to be transferred (securely), combined, remixed and reused across all different environments researchers work in
- In Europe we call this the EOSC Interoperability Framework and we should be working on it globally!

Kati Lassila-Perini:

- CMS research data is not only collision data: there are extensive amounts of metadata necessary to make data (re)usable: content metadata, provenance metadata and contextual metadata
- In order to be able to release data open, data management within the collaborations is crucial
- How to make open science happen?
There are various levels that need to be considered: Researcher (knowledge preservation, data and software skills, **time**), organization/university/institute (Infrastructure, resources, guidelines), collaboration/group (Policies, Agreements, practices)

Tibor Simko:

- Infrastructure at CERN for the release of research level LHC datasets: The CERN open data portal
 - Over 3 petabytes and 1.5 million files
 - Launched in November 2014
 - Collision and simulated datasets for research
 - Derived datasets for education
 - Configuration files and documentation
 - Virtual machines and container images
 - Software tools and analysis example
- Selected observations (on the CERN open data portal):
Build “together”, not “for” -> collaboration is key!
Expect unexpected (be ready to amend and adjust data models)
Open is not enough (make data FAIR)
Data is not enough (you need other components)
- From Open Data to Open Science: Ultimate goal? Facilitate future data reuse; What is the most efficient way to pass the knowledge to future generations? Data + Code + Environment + Workflow = Reusable Science
- REANA Reusable Analyses: run containerised computational workflows

Discussion

What has gone very well when you were implementing open data policies? What were the challenges?

What worked well: rewarding the publication of data/software in the same way than the release of publications; challenge: there is no compliance mechanisms for releasing data on the grant level (Chelle Gentemann)

What worked well: workshops on what are good DMPs (and which should be rejected), developing an understanding of the difference between fair and open data; challenge: visions of open data are often very grand and can sometimes not be immediately translated into practice (Sarah Jones)

What worked well: open data as a bottom up movement: agreements of data release written by the LHC research collaborations in 2011 led to the development of an open data policy on the institutional level -> don't try to impose policy from the outside (Kati Lassila-Perini)

What worked well: CERN open data portal was built before the release of an open data policy -> bottom-up infrastructuring effort that was standardized later into a general policy (Tibor Simko)

PIs are afraid to lose their data (once released it cannot be taken back). How to deal with this fear? Can you create search engines that search across datasets of multiple organizations?

It's a current attempt of EOSC to develop a search engine that makes data discoverable across repositories (Sarah Jones)

Is there something exciting happening with interoperability?

A lot of piloting in this relation going on (Sarah Jones)

How can data on compliance be integrated into subsequent release of policy and in funding decisions?

It's very difficult to check whether researchers comply with funding requirements. There are currently no ways to check this (Sarah Jones)

How can data management be done in an efficient way? What infrastructures are needed to make it easy to open up data?

Skill sharing is very difficult if data is not preserved. Often, making data not (re)usable can take a lot of time from researchers who need to reconstruct their colleagues' analysis practices. Researchers therefore need a long time to understand each other's work. Thus, data management can help them in working more efficiently. (Tibor Simko)

What are actual examples that allow us to convince researchers to adopt open science practices? What are success stories? In astronomy, data is open. But it's very complex and it's hard to generate results. How to convince organizations to improve their open data?

CMS open data workshops allow to engage researchers. Open data has been used for benchmarking. (Kati Lassila-Perini)

If you provide data on higher levels of abstraction, it can be used outside local research contexts. (Chelle Gentemann)

Key takeaways

- Don't talk about open data, talk about data management: to make data open, it needs to be managed well by scientists within their research collaborations. This not only improves the (re)usability of later data releases, but additionally enables researchers to collaborate more effectively within their research contexts.
- Community engagement in the development of open data infrastructures and policies is crucial. Without exchange with the community, policies risk becoming another obstacle for researchers, rather than a support structure and infrastructures are at risk of not being used.
- Rewarding open practices is essential: Open data outputs need to be treated as equally valuable contributions than publications.

Plenary Talk: Promoting Open Data Policies and Practices

Christopher Marcum

Goal: Expanding equitable access to protected public access data

What is open data?

- Open data as an ideal of scientific discovery
- The data access continuum: all data is on a spectrum from open to closed (rarely fully open or entirely closed)
- Not all public access data is open data, but all open data is public access
- All data should try and adhere to something close to the FAIR data principles with the goals to improve "trust in science", "accelerate discovery" and enable "equity" (this can be particularly achieved by increasing reusability and interoperability)
- All public access data can be made fair!
- Findable = metadata, Accessible = clear process, Interoperable = common model, Reuseable = licenses and analytic code

Infrastructures:

- Repository for access to federal government's open datasets: data.gov
- 16 agencies, access to 1438 restricted datasets:
- Access is granted through a standard application process
- data.gov makes datasets discoverable across agencies
- **Virtual Access:**
Opportunity for impactfully expanding access from remote secure locations
Leverage emerging advances including VDCs, cloud, and containerization,

Greater equity in access, should consider air-gap and homographic encryption

- **Tiered access:**

- Define different data levels: identifiable -> anonymized -> aggregated
- Focus is on a single dataset with varying levels of identification and aggregation
- Policies should clearly define limitations of tiers and implications on levels of analysis
- Can be incorporated into tiered-storage systems natively

Discussion

Are there identification risks to making data open and/or fair?

Example: genomic data (you can identify individuals through it) -> tiered access allows to generate data that leaves no traces of the individual

Use encryption services: services that don't display data but only analysis results

What are the most useful datasets on data.gov for the community? What are datasets that are missing?

API translation for data.gov is necessary to develop use statistics, it hasn't been done yet

There are often high barriers to using sensitive data? How to lower them?

It's important to communicate barriers clearly and try and lower them as far as possible, e.g. through virtual identification

It's essential to do user experience research

Key takeaways

- Not all public access data can be open, but all public access data should be FAIR.
- It is essential to lower the barriers for (re)using data as far as possible; for instance through enabling virtual identification and access.
- Tiered access is a possibility to make data accessible to as many users as possible.

Panel Discussion: Developing Open Data Policies

Moderators:

Christopher Marcum

Nokuthula Mchunu (NRF South Africa)

Panelists:

Jamie Boyd (CERN)

Rachel Paseka (NASA)
Stefanie Lumnitz (ESA)

Opening statements

Jamie Boyd:

Development of an open data policy for the CERN experiments working at the Large Hadron Collider

- Concerns of collaborations with regard to making data open: ownership, effort (concern that effort to operate the experiment is not undertaken anymore if researchers can use data without taking part), risk scientific rigor, resources (effort necessary to make data open)
- In 2020, the open data policy was released: It includes an embargo period of 5 years: this was essential in convincing the collaborations to adopt the policy
- Plan for the future: develop policies for the smaller experiments

Stefanie Lumnitz:

- There are various open data policies relating to the different missions of ESA
- Two policy examples: the esa earth observation data policy and the climate change initiative data policy
- The **esa earth observation policy** is applicable per default to the data provided by past, current and future ESA Earth observation missions:
 - To maximize the beneficial use
 - Balanced use of a variety of applications, be it scientific, for public good or commercial
 - Latest update May 2023 including: FAIR Guiding Principle
 - open: ...available and open in a non discriminatory way..., ...preserved and accessible during and beyond mission lifetime ...
 - Full: ...access to all data upon registration accepting ESA terms and conditions...,restraining data, technical and financial constraints...
 - Free: ...free of charge...,... the data is provided at or close to reproduction cost..
- **ESA's Climate Change Initiative Data Policy:** Essential Climate Variable (ECV) data products, with accompanying metadata:
 - Data management, access and long-term stewardship with the producing organization
 - Traceability: input data sources, processing chain and error characteristics
 - encouraged to associate DOIs (digital object identifiers) with released datasets
 - OPEN: .freely available without any restriction on use

- FULL: ...access to all data upon registration.... , ...Early-release CCI data access may be restricted (6 months)
- FREE:...except when third party license conditions apply.
- ...except for large and complex requests with additional cost

Rachel Paseka:

Two open data policy initiatives in 2023 at NASA: Scientific Information Policy for the Science Mission Directorate, NASA Public Access Plan

Scientific Information Policy for the Science Mission Directorate (SMD):

Scope:

- SMD: Astrophysics | Biological & Physical Sciences | Earth Science | Heliophysics | Planetary Science
- All future SMD-funded scientific activities, including new missions and research awards

Context for Development:

- Previous policy (SPD-41) released in 2021
 - Consolidated existing Federal and NASA policy on sharing scientific information
 - Incorporated recommendations from SMD Strategy for Data Management and Computing for Groundbreaking Science 2019-2024
- Policy updates in SPD-41a arose from:
 - Community input via workshops and public comments on draft policy
 - OSTP Memo on Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research
- Development led by the SMD Chief Science Data Office, with input from all SMD divisions through Open Source Science Initiative Council

Content:

Scientific data underlying peer-reviewed manuscripts shall be made publicly available no later than the publication of the peer-reviewed article.

Scientifically useful data associated with a research award shall be made publicly available no later than the end of the award.

Mission data shall be openly available with no period of exclusive access.

- The period for data calibration and validation shall be as short as possible and shall not exceed six months.

Scientific data *should follow FAIR principles*, shall be made reusable with a clear, open, and accessible data license, *and shall be citable with a persistent identifier.*

All SMD-funded scientific activities shall include a data management plan.

SMD proposal reviews: peer reviewed data and software shall be recognized as having commensurate value as peer reviewed manuscripts

SMD Open-Source Science Guidance

For SMD-funded researchers: narrative guidance on policy requirements
Broad scope, for relevance across Divisions

Includes:

- Open Science and Data Management Plan
- Sharing Publications
- Data Management and Sharing
- Software Management and Sharing
- Persistent Identifiers for Investigators
- Sharing Materials for Science Events
- Glossary of Open-Source Science Terms

NASA Public Access Plan for Increasing Access to Results of Scientific Research (DRAFT)

Public release: May 18, 2023

Scope

- Agency-wide: all NASA research, development, and technology programs

Context for Development

- Original NASA Public Access Plan released in 2014
- Updates arose from: OSTP Memo on Ensuring Free, Immediate, and

Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research

Major advancements in the adoption of open science practices since 2014

Development led by NASA Office of the Chief Scientist, with input from all relevant directorates

(e.g., Science Mission Directorate) and offices (e.g., Office of General Counsel)

Feedback provided by OSTP was incorporated prior to public release

Content:

Key Requirements for Scientific Data:

- Scientific data underlying peer-reviewed manuscripts shall be made publicly available no later than the publication of the peer-reviewed article.

- All proposals or project plans submitted to NASA for scientific research funding shall include a Data Management Plan

Components of Plan Relevant to Open Data:

- Updates to NASA Research Data Policies
e.g., NASA Policy Directive 2230.1 - Research Data and Publication Access
- Future work: Guidance and training, infrastructure, compliance processes, and metrics

Next Steps

- Plan is currently open for public comment and public webinar will be held July 17, 2023
- Feedback will inform final plan and its implementation

Discussion

How can we build policies that can account for the increasing amount of data that is being generated?

Embargo period is essential; previous analyses within the collaborations demonstrate how analysis can be done on large datasets most effectively, this knowledge can be used for the external release of data. (Jamie Boyd)

Include community right from the start to be able to decide what are the most useful data products (levels of aggregation) for open release. (Stefanie Lumnitz)

In the implementation of policies, it is crucial to connect with researchers and find out which data is scientifically useful and worth sharing. Make sure infrastructures that can host large datasets are in place. (Rachel Paseka)

Different time ranges for the release of open data within different organizations. Was there discussion on a tiered roll out of open data (releasing later data quicker)?

Embargo periods ensure that data exploitation can take place inside research organizations. For CERN, these embargo periods are essential (Jamie Boyd)

NASA does not allow embargo periods for new missions, for old missions in astronomy it is still allowed (Rachel Paseka)

Who makes data meaningful/(re)usable at CERN? Are there dedicated roles?

Its essential to release simulated data, software, calibration; there are no dedicated roles within the collaborations (works better for some collaborations than others) (Jamie Boyd)

How can we get communities to share their data?

There should already be an infrastructure in place, as well as guidance and incentives to practice open science (Rachel Paseka)

Key takeaways

- Embargo periods for data release can, at times, be helpful in enabling the establishment of open data policies in accordance with the interests of researchers.
- Community engagement is crucial in guaranteeing the success of policy development.
- Policies are agile: they need to be continuously updated and refined through feedback circles.

Clinic Summary: Open Data Sharing

Assessing Existing Policies

-> **Comparison between NASA's and CERN's open data policy**

Three key takeaways:

1. Knowing where (and why) to be vague and where to be specific in different parts of the policy can help
2. Adding a process for versioning/variances/exemptions can circumvent many arguments and create flexibility
3. Definitions are important, including the definitions of mandatory and discretionary action

A question for the larger group:

1. How do we address differences in linguistic, legal adaptation, and cultural differences as we consider international open science policies?

Creating a Policy Resource Group

Three key takeaways:

1. Goal: Make it less overwhelming to create a policy in the interest of science through the guidance of a policy creation tool.
2. Any policy resource we create has to be sufficiently detailed and flexible to work in some of these considerations? It should be agnostic.
3. Could we get an international body take on the endorsement /promotion /governance / branding of this tool (hint: *****)

A question for the larger group (optional):

1. Who Will Develop And Maintain This Policy Tool Platform? And how do we build it in a way that doesn't make it completely overwhelming - aka it needs resources.

Strategic Action Plans Group A

Three key takeaways:

1. Policy should have a process in place. A process that facilitates the steps required for research data management. This can be done at the discipline, institutional, and research facility levels. Handoff responsibility (mandate) to research institution, etc. Take advantage of resources available, e.g. IVOA. (Top down / bottom up)
2. Policy includes information about how research outputs like data are monitored so that researchers have a clear understanding of how the policy will be checked (per the implementation aspect). Policy should show its teeth E.g., OA.Works/Dataseer.
3. Researchers and supporters need to be routed via a workflow where a global notification service that can be leveraged to inform services that researchers need assistance from (services negotiate). For instance, routed to the appropriate repository. Initial work in DataCite on RAiD/maDMPs. A place where best practices/standards can be shared. -> This might facilitate collaboration between the services as well.

A question for the larger group (optional):

1. It's not the researchers job to make Science open, it's everyone else's job to make that happen for researchers. AKA, Team Science. If we leave it to the researcher, it will be a isolated/siloed research.

Strategic Action Plans Group B

Three key takeaways:

1. Get Inspiration From Those With Existing/aligned practices
2. DMPs: machine-readable, public, scalable
3. Make hardware/instrumentation part of the picture

A question for the larger group (optional):

1. What is the responsibility of the researcher vs the organization/infrastructure in developing DMPs?

There needs to be facilitation in developing dmps (somebody who mediates between institutions and researchers)

Depends on the aim of the dmp, if it is to support researchers, it should be developed by researchers, if it's to check whether data management meets funding requirements, it should be done by funders

Focus on suggestions on dmps of science europe

Strategic Action Plans Group B

Three key takeaways:

1. Before/after policy doesn't matter: permanent adjustment is key
2. Implement feedback mechanisms on all organizational scales
3. Reduce entry barriers/complexity: make it easy, it will work better

A question for the larger group:

How do we measure progress of implementation or how do we measure cultural change?

Measure what is the amount of papers that are open vs. those which are closed: -> check which publications measure data -> 20 percent of them uses open data
Need to be more precise on what we measure. Do you measure compliance with a policy/dmp?

Strategic Action Plans Group C

Three key takeaways:

1. **Culture matters!** Usual cultural considerations discussed - and also a recognition that culture can be discipline specific, but infrastructures and formats are often discipline agnostic
2. **Be strategic!** Understand the local level needs and context, to drive opportunities for meaningful impact and culture change
3. **Nurture an interdisciplinary environment!**
Engage different roles to better reflect perspectives for community and capacity building.

A question for the larger group:

1. Is a strategic plan even necessary?? Do we need a **Strategic Plan** or do we just need to **plan on being strategic...**

Open data/research data management/Fair data policy development

Three key takeaways:

1. Ask not only what your researchers should do, (baseline: open repository, clear licence, metadata/PID)
2. Ask also what you can do for your researchers (training and support, infrastructure, credit/reward)
3. Ask what together we can do for the benefit of all mankind (more collaboration possibilities, alignment personal and organisational values)

A question for the larger group (optional):

How can we permeate policy throughout the organisation, especially if support from management is not enthusiastic?

Align values of open science with the values of the organization

Key takeaways

- The "assessing existing policies" clinic stated that it is crucial to understand where to be general and where to be specific in different parts of a policy.

- The clinic "creating policy resource" suggested the development of a policy creation tool which is sufficiently detailed and flexible to make the development of policies less overwhelming.
- According to the "strategic action plan development" clinics, policy should have a procedure that directs through the stages necessary for managing research data. The clinics also recommended that feedback mechanisms at all organizational levels are beneficial to improving policies and monitoring progress. The clinics also suggested that research cultures can be discipline-specific and as a result require customized approaches.
- The "fair data policy development" clinic recommended focusing attention on the benefits of open data, such as more opportunities for collaboration and a better alignment of organizational and individual values.

Day 3: 12th of July

Plenary Talk: How to Do Open Source Software Today

Fernando Pérez

Today, software is essential to science. Do we treat it as such?

IPython and Jupyter - a lesson in the power of open communities

- Open software tools such as Jupyter notebooks have been used for famous discoveries in 21st century in physics, engineering and beyond
- Jupyter models are used by a broad range of players in industry

Jupyter Hub: key technology (with a wide industrial adoption)

- Open, modular, flexible: empower users
- Hosting for equity: all students have the same tools
- Replicates local experience
- But without the tech support nightmare
- Real world tools, not "teaching toys"

This would never have happened under "traditional academic models"

Tools built *by scientists*, for their science!

Differences between traditional academic and open source culture:

	Open Source	Academia
Credit	Distributed	PI & hierarchy
Output/artifacts	Continuous & Project-specific	Discrete papers
Collaborators	Fluid: professionals, volunteers, ...	Structured, funding-dependent
Governance, decision making	Open, community based	Top-down, PI

Authorship	Fluid, roles can evolve, no clear "first/senior" author	Need to say more?
Peer review	Continuous, open, pervasive, friendly	The opposite
Value metric	Utility, need, impact	"Novel and transformative"

Scientific software is a lot more than just code: Community, standard and protocols, software, content and services

Discussion

Difficulty of maintaining open source. What could funding agencies do to recognize and reward open software projects?

Building a culture of closing projects, instead of endless growth; understanding community building as essential part of science/software development

Who could initiate change in the right direction? Do you think open software needs to be a bottom up movement or do funders need to change tactics?

both, bottom up and top down, funders need to acknowledge open software efforts, but researchers need to acknowledge open software development as valuable scientific contribution

Who contributes to open source and who uses open source tools? How do scientists from the global south engage?

Hosting workshops to build capacities (cloud infrastructure) and address research questions relevant in the global south;

Key takeaways

- Computers are scientific instruments: teach researchers how to use them well! It's crucial to teach researchers about how to work with software tools in a sustainable way.
- Traditional academic practice and open source culture differ significantly in terms of values, collaborative structures, hierarchies, and research outcomes. Academic institutions should work to adopt open source approaches that are focused on nonhierarchical collaboration and prioritize community building.

- Incentive structures need to transform: it is still dominant to assess researchers on the basis of publications (impact factor); this needs to be abolished. Instead, there should be a focus on building healthy and productive communities.

Panel Discussion: Open Source from Policy to Practice

Speaker

Stefanie Lumnitz (ESA)

Panelists:

Steve Crawford (NASA)

Codrina Illie

Karthik Ram (UC Berkeley)

Opening statements

Steve Crawford:

- In earth and space science, software is integral to every step of the scientific process: from information gathering by space based detectors to sharing results.
- Stages of reproducibility:
 1. Software is not mentioned
 2. Software is mentioned, but not described
 3. Software is described, but not made available or by request only
 4. Software is made openly available
 5. ...with a permissive license
 6. ...with good documentation and testing
 7. Bonus: Contributed to a generalized package

Challenges in reproducibility:

- Data and plots are shared, but it isn't clear how the plots are derived from the data
- Researcher leaves the field or the software is lost
- Algorithms are described but with insufficient detail to reproduce
- Configurations or steps are not shared

Advantages of open source scientific software:

- Increased reproducibility
- Reuse
- Curation and archiving
- Better understanding of the results
- Credit
- Sustainability

Software highlights at NASA:

NASA Draft Public Access Plan Part C focus on scientific software:

- Scientific Software underlying scholarly publications is made publicly available at the time of publication
- Proposals include a Software Management Plan
- Scientific software should be released with documentation that enables reusability
- Encourage contributions to existing open source software

SMD SPD-41 a: Scientific Information Policy

- Mission scientific software is developed openly
- Recognizes scientific software as a scientific product
- Permissive open source licenses should be used

NASA Software Release policies have also recently been updated

Codrina Illie:

Empower everyone with open source geospatial:

- Provides financial, organizational and legal support to the broader open source geospatial community.
- Serves as an independent legal entity to which community members can contribute code, funding and other resources, secure in the knowledge that their contributions will be maintained for public benefit.
- Mission is to foster global adoption of open geospatial technology by being an inclusive software foundation devoted to an open philosophy and participatory community driven development.

OS geo Incubation:

- Clear structure (governance)
- Framework collaboration with like-minded organizations and institutions: MoUs
- Traceability and accountability
- Projects guidelines to join OSGeo (incubation)
- Events: FOSS4Gs conferences and code sprints

-> Open software has matured in the field, it is no longer an effort of individuals or small collaborations: It needs to be built over time

Karthik Ram:

We need to think about "software sustainability":

- Research software landscape has come a long way: It is much easier to develop software, find support/ community and not (always) explain what an RSE means, however it's still very hard to demonstrate the impact of software
- There is a lot of support for creating software, but very little to sustain it after reaching product market fit: Concepts for software sustainability need to be developed!

Discussion

What are the benefits of creating an open source software policy, or including an open source software element in a policy on the institutional and community level?

Nasa had a open source release policy for 20 years; this sometimes increased the barriers of releasing software -> be iterative in the development (Steve Crawford)

Develop flexible policy structures that help researchers in open sourcing their work (Karthik Ram)

New US security regulation on open source software: How do security issues affect your projects?

Communities need support to meet security requirements (Steve Crawford)

Security is an important issue, should be addressed through regulation (Codrina Illie)

Who takes responsibility when open source software fails?

Using open source is a change in paradigm; if there is an issue with an open source software, you can hire a company to take care of it, in the proprietary world, you would have to wait for software update of the company who produced the software (Codrina Illie)

Think about becoming a collaborator in open source projects to have a stake in the project -> otherwise, open source projects risk "catastrophic success" (Karthik Ram)

Are there any resources for open source projects (how to design policies) in a centralized place?

This might be a current gap. No single institution could do that. (Karthik Ram)

OSI provides guidance on licenses. Still, a centralized space could be useful. (Steve Crawford)

What role can policies play? Where are other instruments needed?

To be part of OS geo, specific requirements have to be met in terms of governance (e.g. no hierarchical structures) (Codrina Illie)

Licenses are necessary to clarify questions of ownership, OSPOs can be really helpful in providing internal guidance (Karthik Ram, Steve Crawford)

From a policy standpoint, how can institutions incentivize their community to contribute back to open source projects?

OSPOs can be crucial in making sure that value is returned to the open source community (Karthik Ram)

Key takeaways

- Open source policies on institutional level are necessary to give clear directions. OSPOs are crucial in facilitating policy development and providing continuous guidance.
- It is a good strategy to include existing best practices in policies that are being developed.
- Open source is no longer a hack in the afternoon, it's a (economical) ecosystem: institutions and funders need to understand that open source can also be commercial.
- Open source is about community! Fostering and maintaining these communities is crucial.
- We need to acknowledge sustainability issues around open source and debate how to resolve them.

Plenary Talk: Towards a software pillar for open science: from policy to implementation

Roberto Di Cosmo (Computer Science professor in Paris, now working at INRIA)

- Software is becoming more and more dominant, "its eating the world",
- Open source is eating the software world

The evolution of open software:

- **First 15 years: 1984-. . . The early revolution:** focus: freedom for users and (especially) developers; keyword: free software
- **The second wave: 1999-. . . Progressive industry adoption:** focus: software quality and reduced cost; keyword: open source (~25th anniversary!)
- **The third wave: 2010-. . . Ecosystems, strategic alignment:** focus: community, organisation, foundations; keyword: governance

- **The fourth wave: 2015-. . . Industry consolidation:** focus: mergers and acquisitions; keyword: control

-> all of these dynamics are now happening at the same time

Today: The infrastructure for (open) collaboration is the new competitive advantage!

Research shows: "Over 20% of articles across all disciplines share software"

-> Therefore: software may be a tool, a research outcome and a research object -> access to the source code is essential!

- Source code is special: evolution over time (projects may last decades the development history is key to its understanding), complexity (millions of lines of code large web of dependencies easy to break, difficult to maintain research software a thin top layer sophisticated developer communities)
- How are we managing our software? -> not very well
- Issues: Reproducibility, maintenance in Academia; Security, integrity, traceability in Industry

International highlights

Paris Call on Software Source code (2019, UNESCO)

40 international experts call to "promote software development as a valuable research activity, and research software as a key enabler for Open Science/Open Research, [...] recognising in the careers of academics their contributions to high quality software development, in all their forms"

-> Open Source in UNESCO recommendations for Open Science, 2021

Software in the EOSC

2020 EOSC SIRS connect scholarly ecosystem via Software Heritage

2021 EOSC Task Force on Infrastructures for Research Software

2022 FAIRCORE4EOSC project WP6 implements SIRS report

2023 INFRAEOSC call on quality of scientific software

What is at stake?

ARDC

Archive for retrieval (reproducibility)

Reference for identification (reproducibility)

Describe for discovery and reuse

Cite/Credit for credit and evaluation

Before ARDC

Development practices and tools (VCS, build system, test suites, CI, code quality, . . .)
Opening up towards a community (documentation, organization, communication) Need training, tooling, infrastructures, best practices

Beyond ARDC

Policies (dissemination, reuse, careers, . . .)

Sustainability (legal, financial, etc.)

Technology transfer Advanced technologies and tools (quality, traceability, etc.)

French National plan for Open Science, 2021-2024: full chapter on open software

Five action lines:

Identifying and highlighting research software production

Technical tools and best practices

Translation and sustainability

National, European, and International coordination

Recognition, evaluation and careers

Forges are not archives!

2015: the first big bad news: Google Code and Gitorious.org shutdown: ~1M endangered repositories broken links in the web of knowledge (my papers too)

Big bad news keep coming in

Summer 2019: BitBucket announces Mercurial VCS sunset

July 2020: BitBucket erases 250.000+ repositories (including research software) Summer

2022: GitLab.com considers erasing all projects that are inactive for a year

In Academia too!

2021: Inria's old gforge is unplugged. . . breaks the Opam build chain for OCaml

Collect, preserve and share all software source code: Preserving our heritage, enabling better software and better science for all: reference catalogs, universal archives and research infrastructures

Software heritage: The largest software archive, a shared infrastructure

Discussion

Which Incentives for practicing open software have worked?

Numerical indicators do not work in measuring contributions. Count quality software contributions in careers and void purely numerical indicators.

Key takeaways

- The infrastructure for (open) collaboration is the new competitive advantage!
- Software may be a tool, a research outcome and a research object -> access to the source code is essential!
- It's crucial to build a common, global repository for open software.
- Avoid proprietarisation: set the default to open
- Establish intelligent and effective incentives: count quality software contributions in careers and void purely numerical indicators.

Panel Discussion: Open Source Software and Hardware in Practice

Moderator:

Chelle Gentemann (NASA)

Panelists:

Julieta Arancio (Universidad Nacional de San Martín Argentina)

Lars Holm Nielsen (CERN)

Javier Serrano (CERN)

Opening statements

Javier Serrano

- Open hardware deserves a place in an open science policy
- Hardware is not fundamentally different to software (Hardware designs are often distributed in the form of code)

Julieta Arancio

- Why people want to use open hardware today: lack of flexibility in instrumentation with proprietary hardware
- Open hardware endeavors are driven by early career researchers: these researchers tend to leave academia since there is no validation structures for open hardware development

Lars Holm Nielsen

- Software development crucially relies on community building

Discussion

How to accelerate the adoption of open hardware?

It's essential to incentivise open hardware production and use: there needs to be more communication and advertisement.

Governance bodies need to develop a clear vision of public/private initiatives and what the roles of these parties are in open source projects. Companies should not be forced to make everything open, public institutions should not be forced to adopt closed models. (Javier Serrano)

Is the legal landscape of open hardware more complex than that of software?

Licenses are crucial in delivering clarity. See for instance the CERN open hardware license which is openly accessible. However, projects often seem to be eager to adopt their own legal standards. (Javier Serrano)

How do you deal with software for open hardware?

There are no common software formats for releasing open hardware. We need free open source software tools to access and publish hardware. (Javier Serrano)

The CERN Open hardware license has different versions. Which of these has gained the most traction?

There is a lot of uptake of the permissive variant outside of CERN. (Javier Serrano)

How can we move the development of policy forward?

Establishing an OSPO and demonstrating the societal value of open source (Lars Holm Nielsen)

Show that there is a risk of incompatibility if hardware is not open, especially in the context of complex scientific instruments (Julieta Arancio)

How can the uptake of open hardware/software be advertised to funders?

Open source can reduce friction by making manufacturing possible for a larger group of actors. (Javier Serrano)

Policies can articulate what institutions want to do with open projects. (create new collaborations ect.) (Lars Holm Nielsen)

Can we expect open hardware projects to be sponsored by industry?

What is one thing we can do to have a successful open hardware project? What is one thing we should avoid?

Commercial activity is a must for open hardware projects. This can be an advantage for the sustainability of projects. (Javier Serrano)

What are implementation details that are crucial for an OSPO?

Including open hardware into the OSPO mandate. Focusing on supporting researchers in open sourcing their work. Involving the technology transfer team.
(Javier Serrano)

Don't forget about the people: focus on communities of practice and their needs.
(Lars Holm Nielsen)

Key takeaways

- OSPOs are crucial in coordinating open software and hardware efforts.
- Open hardware is a crucial element of open science.
- Licenses and policies can bring clarity and define pathways for private/public partnerships in open hardware and software projects.

Clinic 3: Open Source Policies

Strategic action plan development A

Three key takeaways:

1. We need better data about the usage and production of open source software in scientific communities and institutions to inform relevant policies and investments
2. Data about usage/production would help: prioritize institutional support/funding; understand unmet needs of research staff; support the computational literacy needs of students/trainees.
3. Possible data sources and approaches
 - a. Develop an instrument to gauge research software usage at institutional level (are OSPOs already doing this?)
 - b. Mine the literature and open syllabus corpora to understand what authors and instructors are using (e.g. softcite, CZ Software Mentions)
 - c. Analyze open source repositories by institution
 - d. Analyze domain-specific resource repositories for recommendations of open source tools by discipline (e.g. NIH Comparative Genomics Resource, Online Bioinformatics Resources Collection)

A question for the larger group:

Are bottom-up approaches to inform institutional-level support of open source (both the production and usage) more effective than waiting for a top-down policy framework?

Strategic action plan development B

Three key takeaways:

1. "Hardware is strategically critical but nobody is talking about it" "hardware is really neglected, but there's nothing there" "I've spent so much time thinking about

- hardware but there's nobody to talk to about it"
2. What is open hardware? FAIR hardware with an R for Repairability. Work on the concept and communication about it, including through use cases
 3. Open science and tech transfer

A question for the larger group:

Is there a workflow for publishing open hardware that is best practice for the community? Is there a repository? How to consider publishing open hardware that is interoperable with data and software

Open source hardware association, FAIR group on open hardware, github for designs

Strategic action plan development C

Three key takeaways:

1. Create some version of an OPSO at your institution
 - a. Include hardware from the get go
2. Try to pilot an OSPO with a limited scope to get buy in from leadership.
 - a. Potential lessons coming down the line from various emerging academic OSPOS
3. Various existing tools exist that can be brought to bear on impact

A question for the larger group:

How would you manage the costs of running the OSPO and the cost of open sourcing software/hardware?

There should be studies that show the monetary advantages of open sourcing as opposed to the cost of an OSPO (there are studies in the context of software, but also in the context of hardware)

There is communities who try to provide resources that normally an OSPO would provide

Strategic action plan development D

Three key takeaways:

- **A few principles to follow:** meet people where they are, be iterative with a process of defining and testing your assumptions, check with community to ensure you're having the effect you want.
- **Define archetypes of who your policy affects.** For example, Open Source enthusiasts / inexperienced but interested / disinterest and only want to not be bothered.
- **Define the most important questions to answer that help you design an action plan for them:** what do they care about, what action you need from them, and how to either incentivize them to take action, or reduce barriers to it.

A question for the larger group (optional):

How to avoid getting trapped into your own assumptions?

Key takeaways

- Strategic action plan development A: There needs to be data on the use of open software resources to inform future policy.
- Strategic action plan development B: Open hardware is crucial in the open science landscape but no one is talking about it. Concepts such as “FAIR hardware” need to be developed.
- Strategic action plan development C: Creating a version of an OSPO at your institution is crucial to measure the impact of open source and to support researchers in open sourcing their work.
- Strategic action plan development D: To make sure that the policy has the desired impact, it is essential to define a strategic action plan that is implemented gradually.

Day 4: 13th of July

Plenary Talk: Open Science and Research Integrity: Rosie general guidelines on responsible open science

Rosemarie Bernabe

Available Guidance on open science practice: Eu recommendation of open science, Unesco recommendations on open science, FAIR and CARE

-> OS thus contains a number of sources of normativity – what counts as good or responsible OS – and this is one source of challenges in itself, i.e., in satisfying some objectives, it is seen as failing others.

The ROSIE declaration on Research Environment and Infrastructures:

2.1. Policy reforms and OS advocacy are crucial for creating a culture that promotes, supports, and rewards OS. A policy environment conducive to responsible OS requires aligned action on the European, national, and institutional levels.

2.3. Cooperation and exchange of information between policymakers, the research community, and the public are particularly important. Systematic, evidence based analysis and operational synthesis are needed for better informed and aligned OS policies on national and international levels.

2.5. RFOs should be aware and sensitive to the fact that OS practices and regulations in different countries are diverse. The baseline for openness requirements should be clear and attainable to all European countries. The ROSIE declaration on Protection of Research Participants, the Environment, Ecosystems, and Cultural Heritage

3.3. Protecting the privacy and control interests of research participants and their communities is essential in an open data environment. Researchers, research ethics committees, RPOs, and policymakers should analyze the risks of reidentification and dual use in different fields and develop governance mechanisms and technical solutions to address these risks. Exploring other approaches to protect privacy, other than anonymization, is increasingly becoming important and is thus recommended.

The ROSIE declaration on open data:

- RFOs should: incentivise data sharing through, for example, the inclusion of open data requirements in data management plans.
- Institutionalize and incentivise data sharing and compliance with FAIR and CARE principles;
- Researchers should: collect, analyse, and present research data with the prospect of making it open and reusable; ensure that research data is properly documented, formatted, and stored to facilitate findability and reusability;

The ROSIE declaration on Researcher evaluation:

In accordance with DORA and CoARA recommendations, research performance assessment systems should prioritize quality and openness of the research results over the quantity of published papers. In the evaluation of a researcher's performance, RPOs and RFOs should use a multidimensional approach; bibliometric criteria should not be the only or main criteria. Evaluation systems should also consider the potential positive societal impact of research in accordance with OS and research integrity principles.

The ROSIE declaration on citizen science:

Citizen science offers a potential for socially relevant research and innovation, however, the involvement of citizen scientists without proper support can potentially be an ethics and integrity challenge. Policymakers, RFOs, RPOs, and researchers are responsible for promoting and supporting citizen science. This is done specifically by ensuring support throughout the research lifecycle, through the provision of adequate funding, training, flexible grant structures that accommodate extended timeline research, and encouraging collaborations and building synergies between researchers and other stakeholders.

The ROSIE declaration on training and education:

Policymakers and RPOs should ensure that training and education in responsible OS focuses on the entire research lifecycle and start early-on, integrating the development of relevant attitudes and skills into higher education and perhaps even high school curricula.

The ROSIE declaration on Inclusivity:

Researchers should be aware of potential biases in research related to gender, ethnicity, age, disability, epistemological frameworks, and other factors and act to ensure that responsible OS practices promote equity, inclusiveness, and diversity.

RPOs should recognise potential global inequities in access to OS infrastructure and act to promote global justice and support the needs of researchers in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). There is a great need for policymakers, RFOs, RPOs, and researchers from high-income countries to provide support to institutions from LMICs in building their capacities, exchanging good practices, and establishing infrastructure conducive to OS.

Key takeaways

- OS contains a number of sources of normativity – What counts as good or responsible OS – and this is one source of challenges in itself, i.e., in satisfying some objectives, it is seen as failing others.
- Codes of conduct (for research integrity) are not ready for open science: only the Austrian and French codes of conduct actively support open science -> There is a long way to go -> Rosie declaration aims to address this issue

Plenary Talk: Implementing Open and Reproducible Science in biomedicine

Ulrich Dirnagl

Quality problems in preclinical biomedicine:

- Internal validity of preclinical biomedical research is low (lack of blinding, randomization, etc.)
- Power is exceedingly low, false positives and inflated effect sizes abound, hence reproducibility is low
- Study designs and statistical analysis are often flawed
- '(Spectacular) Story telling' through selective ('flexible') use of data
- Only positive results are published: 'Negative' publication bias almost absolute.

→ **Preclinical biomedicine has a quality problem!**

Investigating the replicability of preclinical cancer biology:

<https://elifesciences.org/articles/71601>

Patient / stakeholder engagement (PSE) – Patient public involvement (PPI):

„With only 23 trials identified in this report, we estimate that far less than 1% (23/371,159) of clinical trials engage patients meaningfully and actively.“

Many countries do not have access to a large portion of the published medical research literature

Open data remains the exception in biomedical research!

The QUEST Center for Responsible Research

PLoS Biol. 2020 Feb 11;18(2):e3000576; <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000576>

More information: quest.bihealth.org

BIH QUEST
Center for Responsible Research

QUEST Approaches

- **Quality assurance:** promote compliance of preclinical and clinical research with standards and guidelines on design, conduct, analysis and reporting.
- **Education:** develop and implement training and teaching resources on experimental and study design, methods to reduce bias, new modes of publishing, open science, etc.
- **Open Science:** improve the accessibility and transparency of BIH research and its results through Open access and Open data.
- **Rewards and incentives:** develop, implement, and assess the impact of novel indicators incentives and metrics for rewarding researchers, appropriating funding and awarding academic degrees.
- **Stakeholder engagement:** develop, support, and evaluate patient and stakeholder engagement activities throughout the entire process of biomedical research
- **Meta-Research:** identify opportunities for improving research practice and obtain evidence for the impact of its activities through 'research on research'.
- **Think tank:** act as advisors to stakeholders in biomedicine from funders to politics.

Strategies and tools:

- Open Science Services, e.g. Electronic Laboratory Notebook

- Educational programs
- Open Science – *Dashboard, Open and Responsible Research*: <https://quest-dashboard.charite.de/>
- Open Science: QUEST Toolbox - Fiddle (shiny app)

Where and how to publish null neutral results: <https://doi.org/10.1042/CS202011>

- Benchmarking university medical centers: <https://journals.plos.org/plosmedicine/article?id=10.1371/journal.pmed.1004175>; <https://quest-cttd.bihealth.org>
- Patient and stakeholder engagement: Training, networking, consultation
- **Open Data LOM at Charité and other responsible research awards:**

Automated identification and rewarding of OD, 300.000 Euros for 2023 allocated on institutional level („Einrichtungsebene“) to incentivize the set up of open data facilitating structures, knowledge base, support etc...

-> Awards for open data reuse (reuse needs to be awarded as well!!)

- **Professorship Application Service Portal:** asking how applicants for professorship envision open science

“The Charité attaches great importance to transparent, replicable research and supports the objectives of Open Science (Open Access, Open Data). This includes the registration of studies in registries (clinicaltrials.gov, DRKS, etc.), the preregistration of studies, and the publication of negative and zero results. **How have you been pursuing these goals so far and what are your plans for the future?**”

Major barriers / bottlenecks / challenges:

- # 1 Brains of scientists, leadership and administrators are hard wired to equate the impact and even purpose of their research with journal reputation and 3rd party funding
- # 2 Responsible research is a state of mind, which requires additional resources
- # 3 Piloting is easy, but ‚line function‘ hard

Discussion

How to avoid hesitancy from researchers?

Staged approach and a lot of dialogue with different stakeholders

Has benchmarking of open science practices changed open science behaviors?

It's hard to say, but it has triggered a discussion within the charitee and other biomedical institutions

What are the most impactful steps after a policy has been published?

Implementing policies while they are being created.

Are there prizes that award public participation in open science such as Hackathons?

Good idea, could be pursued further.

Key takeaways

- There are quality issues in biomedical research: e.g., confirmation bias, inflation bias ect.
- In biomedical research, open science practices are still the exception: Patients are rarely involved, papers are frequently inaccessible online, and open data is the exception.
- QUEST is a way to tackle these issues through various strategies such as training and education, patient enrollment, awards for open data (re)use and considering open science practices in employment processes.

Panel Discussion: Reproducibility, Reusability, and Reward Systems

Moderation:

Erin McKiernan (Open Research Funders Group)

Speakers:

Neil Jacobs (UKRN)

Heidi Seibold (GRN)

Daniel Spichtinger

Toma Susi (University of Vienna, CoARA)

Opening statements

Neil Jacobs:

Open research in three disciplines: Reproducibility, Reuse, Recognition

- **Arts practice research (theater, music, etc)**

Openness and transparency: Little consensus on what this means, for whom, why, how, or when; Very limited resources

Reproducibility: Not clear how this is meaningful. Focus more on positionality, ethics, authenticity / integrity

Reuse: Complex ethical questions, balancing interests of communities, creative work, and scholarship

Recognition: As much outside academia as within it

- **Microbiology** (specifically for veterinary science)

Openness and transparency: Open data is standard / required, in public repositories like NCBI/GenBank. However, metadata is sometimes not standardized
Computational science shares software; lab science not Pre-prints becoming more common, to timestamp findings (lengthy peer review)

Reproducibility: Not much explicit replication (though implicit). Journals won't publish it.

Reuse: Widespread data reuse, but various data ethics and commercialisation constraints

Recognition: Impact factors still matter, despite acknowledgement of their limitations

- **Economics**

Openness and transparency: Open data, code and pre-registration increasingly expected, and ufl methodological transparency, esp for top journals; Potential conflicts of interest (business collaborations)

Reproducibility

Crisis avoided by very transparent reporting. Data often embargoed, limiting direct replication/generalization by others; Data reuse if available, eg increasingly for machine learning (though slow take-up)

Recognition: Publication in the top journals. Potentially fewer career pressures than other fields, more stable careers, better integrity

Heidi Seibold:

Initiatives that tackle issues of open science:

- German Reproducibility Network - a roof network of open science and reproducibility initiatives in Germany
- The Turing Way - a community and an online book about reproducible, ethical and collaborative data science
- Open Science Initiative in Medicine - a group of researchers at LMU Munich

Community management matters!!

Must-haves:

- A clear purpose
- Shared values
- A welcoming environment
- Individuals that drive things forward

No-goes:

- Shouting and foul language
- Predominantly male groups
- Timing of meetings that excludes members/groups
- Leadership that does not care about community management

Daniel Spichtinger:

How to enable data (re)use?

Context

- Policymakers and research funders increasingly seek to promote the open sharing of scientific data
- Secondary use/reuse of data plays an important role in these initiatives, since the scientific and societal value of open data can only be realized if this data, once shared, is actually reused
- What influences whether research data is actually reused? Starting point for the study on data reuse conducted for the LBG OIS Center 2018/2019

Methods

- Exploratory qualitative approach: data was gathered using semi-structured oral interviews, plus written follow-up questions.
- Sample of 24 participants, including reusers and intermediaries from diverse scientific fields and countries

Findings: the 8th factor

• Subjectification:

how researchers develop a habit of reusing data, coming to see this practice as part of their professional identity.

Researchers described this process using a variety of terms, like the development of a reuse 'mindset,' while intermediaries often spoke in terms of developing researchers' 'awareness' of data reuse.

For some, this awareness was linked to using a particular product or service (for example a specific repository). For others it was a question of creating purpose-built settings where researchers can work out how and under what conditions they can benefit from data reuse, as well as grapple with its consequences.

Toma Susi:

COARA: COALITION FOR ADVANCING RESEARCH ASSESSMENT

NEED FOR ASSESSMENT REFORM

- There is broad agreement from the research community on the urgent need to reform existing ways of assessing research.
- Assessment processes relying predominantly on journal- and publication- based metrics can be a hurdle to the recognition of diverse contributions and may negatively affect the quality and impact of research. They also contribute to an unhealthy research culture and an unaffordable publication system, and do not incentivise the adoption of Open Science practices.
- Building on progress made so far (DORA, Leiden Manifesto, Hong Kong Principles), the Agreement establishes a common direction for research assessment reform, while respecting organizations' autonomy. It is based on shared principles, 10 commitments, and a timeframe (1 & 5 years) for reforms.

4 CORE COMMITMENTS (WHAT)

1. Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research, in accordance with the needs and the nature of the research.
2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.
3. Abandon the inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular the inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and *h*-index.
4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment.

6 SUPPORTING COMMITMENTS (HOW)

5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to.
6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes.
7. Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.
8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.

9. Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.
10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.

REPORTING & TIMEFRAME

Based on **voluntary self-assessment** and reporting to peers. Agreement includes touch-base points in years 1 and 5 after signature to communicate progress, based on **self-assessment**.

- **By year 1** signatories share how their organisation **has started the process** of reviewing or developing criteria, tools and processes.
 - Guidance and templates under preparation (Summer 2023)
- **By year 5** signatories have regularly **demonstrated progress** towards reviewing, developing and evaluating criteria, tools and processes that fulfil the core commitments.

-> The Agreement is **only the starting point!** Changes to be developed and implemented by the Coalition.

THE COALITION IN A NUTSHELL

- **The Coalition offers a space for its members to learn from others' experiences**, to advance the process of research assessment reform in Europe and beyond.
- **Signatory organisations**, having subscribed to the Overarching Principles and Code of Conduct, are invited to become members of the Coalition.
- The **Constitutive Assembly**, the first meeting of the General Assembly of members of the Coalition, took place on 1 December 2022.
- Coalition members are invited to be involved in **Working Groups** and other Coalition activities.
 - First batch of Working Groups selected on 12 July 2023!

Discussion

What can policies do in enabling more reproducible research?

Policies can give people the resources to engage in open science. However, it's crucial to develop infrastructures (such as Zenodo) that make it very easy to publish resources. (Heidi Seibold)

It's essential to align incentive structures with policies. A well researched and preserved paper should be worth more than a sloppy paper. (Toma Susi)

Consider how you track progress when drafting policies and what actions you take when they are not followed. (Neil Jacobs)

How can different disciplines decide on which incentive structures to implement?

It varies between disciplines, there is no clear answer. (Toma Susi)

Should academic publishers engage with CoARA?

Academic publishers are not part of this discussion. (Toma Susi)

How can institutions translate commitments into practice? This needs funding. Is the CoARA team thinking about this?

There is debate about how to allocate resources. But it's not only about money. It's about developing large actor networks that enable culture change. (Toma Susi)

There is much more loyalty to disciplines than to individual institutions. How can we draw in disciplinary guilds (e.g., American society for crystallography) to affect culture change in open science?

Academies of science (might be the equivalent to disciplinary guilds in Europe) are not primary research assessors. Still, it might be interesting to think about their effect on culture. (Toma Susi)

(Re)use of data: often very poor. Is it really worth saving all this data if it's not used. Will we have to decide sometimes which data to preserve and which to delete?

Since it is not clear which data will become interesting in the future, researchers should try and preserve their data even if they think it might not be interesting in the future. A quantitative measurement of (re)use is quite difficult. (Daniel Spichtinger)

Trust in research data/software: trust is closely connected to the institution; institutions need to guarantee the reliability of research data. Institutions need to take responsibility. How can that be implemented in policies?

Often, institutions don't play a crucial role in researchers developing trust in data. Researchers tend to look at data and decide based on how they perceive the quality if they want to use it. (Daniel Spichtinger)

Openness is the opposite of trust. By establishing transparency, trust is not necessary. (Toma Susi, Neil Jacobs)

How about awarding prizes on the collective level? Award prizes to institutions that implement good open science practices?

We need proper positions for data stewards and software engineers. (Heidi Seibold)

What could we do, as we get home to our organizations?

Refocus on scientific norms (disinterestedness, communality, ect.,) (Neil Jacobs)

Build community! (Heidi Seibold)

Reward and recognition systems are the lever to make open science possible (Toma Susi)

Key takeaways

- Open science must be able tackle a range of highly diverse disciplines; this necessitates the development of different incentives and policy procedures.
- There are initiatives that can help you address the question of reproducibility such as the German Reproducibility Network and the Turing Way.
- Community management matters: establish shared values and find motivated individuals that drive developments forward.
- Encouraging researchers to consider data reuse as a modus operandi of scientific research should be a key priority. Otherwise, data spaces risk becoming data graveyards. "Build it and they will come" does not work.
- Provide researchers with "safe spaces" for experimenting with data re-use in their activities (e.g. through EOSC, data spaces, infrastructures etc).
- A very broad actor base (especially on the institutional level) is necessary to transform research assessment practices in academia.
- CoARA is an opportunity for institutions to think deeply about what they value and want to promote, and tailor assessment criteria to support that (Coara enables Institutional freedom AND responsibility) -> it needs to be global to become successful

Clinic 4 Review: Reproducible, Reusable and Rewarding Policies

Strategic action plan A

Three key takeaways:

1. How to do a SAP: Assess local priorities, points of leverage (persona), tactics; for each persona, - how to get their attention [success stories], incentivise action [prizes], make their lives easier [fix the plumbing].
2. Where this is a collective action problem, then draw from the research on that kind of challenge
3. Fix the plumbing (again)

A question for the larger group:

1. What is the one x-disciplinary policy action that might help with reproducibility?

Build on previous findings in developing your reproducibility concept.
(Re)use your data yourself.

Have others try to replicate your findings.

Strategic action plan B

Three key takeaways:

1. Message to top level management: OS won't go away. We talk about the competitiveness of the institution.
2. Do first steps, even if it is not perfect. Don't wait for others to establish cultural change
 - a. check existing KPI, customize with OS perspectives (e.g. include research data, software)
 - b. Incentivize re-use (funding streams, includes dashboards to follow provenance)
 - c. Try new ideas (brokerage services for data which is findable - but not yet reusable - establish a pipeline to transfer money to add e.g. more metadata)
3. Open Science - esp. Open Source software is entry card for visibility, access to networks. TEACH it to ECR **and** PIs (leading by example)

A question for the larger group:

What are the selling points for top management?

Promote reproducibility through successful examples. Don't start when you have a perfect strategy; get started early to generate examples

Point to prestigious organization who are implementing reproducibility strategies

Arguing how open science unfriendly environments will lead to several disadvantages for institutions: e.g., early career researchers will expect an open science friendly environment

Pick up the fears of management: Brain drain, losing grants ect.

Assessing existing policies

Three key takeaways:

1. ... *Ready For It?*
 - a. Incentives without support and infrastructure
 - i. Also true for internal team - it is not reasonable to ask a research administrator to assess compliance/adherence without training/guidance
2. *All Too Well*
 - a. Asking researchers "How have you made your work open?" is a fine starting point for policy compliance
 - b. Ultimately, for researchers to treat a policy seriously, though, there needs to

be some form of enforcement 🥕 or 🗣️...or so easy that it simplifies their research processes

3. *Tolerate It*
 - a. Ultimately, if we value open science, we need to incentivize it and enforce those incentives. Otherwise, we aren't really valuing it.

A question for the larger group:

1. Are we prepared to be open about what we learn along the way?

Creating a policy resource

Three key takeaways:

1. *Breathe*
 - a. Key issues: Huge complexity and quantity of info needed; also need structure that makes it user friendly and less terrifying!
2. *Sparks Fly*
 - a. Winning strategies: Building on existing open source solutions, and community crowdsourcing of resources, examples, good practices
3. *Blank Space:*
 - a. Remaining gaps: Pulling resources together, assigning tasks, tech development, and scaling.

A question for the larger group:

1. How to disseminate, promote adoption. not lose momentum. and pre-map responsibilities to share load

Open AIRE policy clinic

Three key takeaways:

1. DMP -> RMP
 - a. Added value of a DMP/RMP
 - b. Distinction between data for reproducibility and data for reuse
 - c. Other types of outputs should be included: software, hardware, workflows, ...
 - d. Modular approach to creating and filling in templates
2. Support
 - a. Science Europe example: enhanced with more content towards RMPs, e.g. links between outputs, overarching standards question
 - b. Network for support and training of RDM policy implementation; helpdesk
 - c. DMP platforms to reduce friction and incentivise good practices + Open source solutions are missing for certain DM
3. RMP as digital object
 - a. "Living document" with versioning mechanisms and connection with exploitation
 - b. Openness of the RMP itself

A question for the larger group:

“Should we be asking institutions or infrastructures to write components of the DMPs with us?”

Key takeaways

- The “strategic action plan” clinics asserted that success stories, prizes for reproducible practices and concrete guidelines from and for a research community are essential in facilitating reproducibility. To convince top management, it's important to argue how open science (in particular open software) can give visibility to an institution and enable the creation of new partnerships.
- The “assessing existing policies” clinic concluded that incentivisation and enforcement need to be equally present in policies.
- The “creating a policy resource” clinic suggested that the pooling of policy resources could benefit from building on existing open source solutions, community crowdsourcing of resources and examples and good practices.

Day 5: 14th of July

Plenary Talk: Incentivising Open Science

Dr Maria Camila Díaz

How might we consider open science as making possible other things like fair access to research?

Colombian national open science policy

POLICY CONTEXT

- Inspired by the values of quality, integrity, collective benefit, equity and justice, diversity and inclusion, and has been developed after the 2018 discussions about the Publindex model and the necessary transition to more responsible and ethical models for scientific communication and the evaluation of science itself
- Developed in response to the commitments made with the OECD and the call made by UNESCO through the Open Science Recommendation 2021.
- Aligns the efforts of all the actors of the National Science, Technology and Innovation System in order to achieve the goal of having a science that is "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" (UNESCO, 2022).

Why an Open Science Policy in Colombia?

- To provide a framework for the different efforts made in the country (NSSTI)
- To Level the playing field on scientific information sharing gaps.
- To consolidate publicly funded scientific knowledge as a common good.
- Open Science as an enabler for participatory science and science democratization.

Problems to solve

- Definition of policies, guidelines and procedures for funders, research institutions
- Insufficient infrastructure and know-how for knowledge sharing
- Lack of incentives for Open Science practices
- Lack of local capacities among researchers on Open Science practices
- Not enough guidance and resources to comply on Open Science requirements
- How to recognize and integrate other systems of knowledge beyond the traditional scientific model

Outcomes of the policy

Our Understanding of Open Science is framed in this four principles:

- Making multilingual knowledge available, accessible and reusable for all
- Increasing scientific collaboration and the exchange of data and information for the benefit of science and society
- Enabling the open participation of citizens in processes of social appropriation of knowledge from their roles, knowledge, contexts and practices
- Promoting a more transparent and cooperative science that privileges inclusion, integrity, equity, justice and diversity

Open Science Policy Components

- Open scientific knowledge
- Open Science Infrastructures
- Social appropriation of science, technology and innovation
- Public communication of science

Policy objectives

“Increase the **visibility, access, reproducibility and usefulness of Colombian scientific, technological and innovation resources**, products and results, expanding training, appropriation, institutionalization and Open Science infrastructures in the country”

Specific objectives

1. Strengthen the governance of Colombia's Open Science model.
2. Create a culture of openness, dialogue, inclusion and social responsibility of the actors that generate knowledge in the country
3. Institute a system of metrics and incentives to promote, value and recognize the Open Science practices
4. Strengthen and consolidate the knowledge capacities of the strategic actors of Open Science in the country.
5. Optimize the use and enhance the Colombian infrastructures available to advance Open Science practices
6. Strengthen and consolidate the knowledge, capacities of the strategic actors of Open Science in the country.

PROGRESS

Open Scientific Knowledge

- Guidelines to promote the culture of management and openness of scientific publications
- Guidelines to foster a culture of management and openness of research data
- Guidelines for the digital preservation of Colombian scientific knowledge heritage
- Metadata Guidelines for Research Data Repositories of the Colombian Network of Scientific Information (2022).
- MinCiencias Research Data Repository (2022-2023)

CHALLENGES

- Define the regulatory framework that allows the implementation of each of the components of Open Science in the country.
- Achieve a culture of openness of scientific information and data.
- Guarantee open access to scientific results and data, based on open scientific publications, self-archiving, interoperable infrastructures, capacity building and long-term preservation of scientific knowledge.
- Articulate the model of evaluation, metrics and incentives with Open Science practices.
- Develop, promote and strengthen infrastructures for the management, retrieval and access to research results and data; as well as participation and exchange with national and international Open Science initiatives
- Harmonize with norms regarding the protection of personal data, intellectual property, security and human rights, among others
- Understand the scope of this policy in the scientific and technological development of the country, the relationship of higher education with industry, state and civil.
- Converge the open science policy with the evaluation model of science in the country. An evaluation model that allows to generate coherence between the open science policy, infrastructure, science, technology and innovation indicators and the evaluation of research.

The future of open science policies in Columbia

Social appropriation of science, technology and innovation Policy.

Integral Public Policy on Ancestral and Traditional Knowledge (in process)

“Generate capacities and conditions to guarantee the recognition, safeguarding, protection and social appropriation of the living systems of ancestral and traditional knowledge of the Indigenous, Natives, Black, AfroColombian, raizales and palenquero communities in Colombia”

Definition of missions for open science

- Benefit from the knowledge, conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, its goods and ecosystem services
- Guarantee food sovereignty and the right to food
- Ensure sustainable energy generation, access and use for all Colombians.
- Assure the food safety, health and wellbeing of the population in the national territory.
- End all forms of violence in Colombia

Discussion

Harmonizing the new policy with existing policies is a big challenge.

What are current plans of integrating indigenous people in the development of open science policies?

Indigenous knowledge opens up for various considerations. There are different systems of knowledge within indigenous communities; How can oral practises be recognised as scientific practises? (-> it's important to take notes); How can these knowledge systems be integrated with other ministries, like health? and who will profit financially from using indigenous knowledge?

How can researchers be credited for their engagement in open science?

There is the attempt to design measurement systems that capture how research is socially appropriated. It's also crucial to recognize teaching activities and science communication projects.

Key takeaways

- Open science policy should not be thought of as an end in itself, but as way of enabling equitable access to research and tackling societal problems.
- By focusing on the “social appropriation of science, technology and innovation”, the Columbian open science policy places a focus on the ways in which open science allows research to become meaningful for society.
- To refocus the objectives of open science on societal concerns, it is crucial to define missions that open science should be addressing.

Plenary Talk: Building a Culture of Open Science: Can we deliver?

Geeta Swamy (Duke University)

Key Players for Building an Equitable, Inclusive Open Science Future:

- Government Agencies
- Coalitions
- Academic Institutions
- Individual Researchers

Government Agencies' Role: Creating Momentum:

- White House Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) Guidance to Make Federal Funded Research Available Without Delay
- Federal funder requirements for data management and sharing plans
- Federal funding opportunities, workshops and resources via various agencies to support open science activities
- CENDI providing online resources for the public to learn about open science initiatives

- NASA's Transform to Open Science (TOPS) initiative and the Year of Open Science 2023

Coalition Building, Gaining Momentum: The Higher Education Leadership Initiative for Open Scholarship (HELIOS)

- Emerged from NASEM Roundtable
- Institutional Leadership involved – Presidents, Vice Presidents for Research
- Facts and figures: 95 campuses, high level representative to 4 working groups who president/provost selects.
- Goals: Building the culture together - working groups are practicing what we value

-> HELIOS' trainings, incentives, and infrastructure are open and aligned across professional societies, federal agencies, philanthropies

Academic institutions

Implementing an Open Scholarship Strategy at the Institutional Level: policy, incentives communities, user interface, infrastructure

Policy:

- Research Data policy updates
- Research Quality Management Program
- Research Onboarding

Incentives:

- Changes to Appointments, Promotion and Tenure (APT) processes

Communities:

- Shared dataset citations published on Scholars@Duke
- Resource Offices (Duke Offices of Research Integrity and Initiatives)
- Research Town Hall meetings

User interface:

- myRESEARCHpath
- myRESEARCHhome
- Research Data Repository

Infrastructure:

- Research Data Repository
- Data Curation Services
- LabArchives Electronic Research Notebook

Research Data Policy phases of work:

BACKGROUND & SCOPE (2020)

Convene workgroups: Ownership/Access, Retention/Transfer, Management/Analysis

Review existing Duke and peer institution policies
Draft initial policy statements

SOCIALIZATION (spring - fall 2021)

Community engagement, faculty, staff, leadership
Research Town Halls
Circulate draft policy via RFI for public comment
Review and share RFI feedback

TOWARDS IMPLEMENTATION (fall 2021- summer 2022)

Convene workgroups to discuss RFI feedback, and process/implementation needs
Discussions to consider resourcing, survey
Finalize policy and associated FAQs and guidance documents

TARGETED ROLLOUT (2022)

Release policy in advance of effective date
Will be effective January, 2023
Continue efforts associated with data-related process refinement

Supporting Data Sharing and Management Planning at Duke

- COORDINATION HUB FOR DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN CONSULT
REVIEW RESEARCH TOWNHALLS
- LABARCHIVES ELECTRONIC RESEARCH NOTEBOOK
- DATA CURATION SERVICES + RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORY
- MYRESEARCHPATH + MYRESEARCHHOME

Key Principles of Building a Culture of Open Science for the Individual Researcher:

- **Inclusive:** All stakeholders need to participate
- **Comprehensive:** Education, oversight and accountability
- **Multifaceted:** Holistic approach across all dimensions of research integrity
- **Pragmatic:** Provide resources and tools to make it “easy” to do the right thing
- **Empowering:** Empower community and stakeholders to speak up

Discussion

How can you convince leadership to attribute resources?

Talk about success stories
Demonstrate how research community has benefited from open data sharing (e.g., training and education)

Research integrity offices are often associated with imposing rules and requirements. Can this perception be transformed?

It's crucial to transform this perception by embedding research integrity issues in the research process and prompting support structures for researchers.

Key takeaways

- Governmental organisations, academic institutions, coalitions, and individual researchers are important stakeholders in constructing an equitable, inclusive open science future.
- Data sharing continues to face barriers at the technical, legal and organizational levels where individuals lack knowledge or skills to share data appropriately and sharing data is often deemed too risky.
- Can we build a culture that creates inclusivity across: Career Stage, Scholarly Disciplines, Academic Promotion/Tenure, Sponsors?

Plenary Talk: African Open Science Platform

Nokuthula Mchunu (NRF South Africa)

Rethinking the “A” in FAIR: Issues of Data Access and Accessibility in Research

Digital open science tools are mainly located in the US!

Unesco recommendations on open science

Making science more:

- Accessible
- Inclusive and,
- Equitable

-> **How can we ensure this?**

African Open Science Platform (AOSP) - Vision and Strands

“African scientists are at the cutting edge of contemporary, data intensive science as a fundamental resource for a modern society. They are innovative global exponents and advocates of Open Science and leaders in addressing African and Global Challenges.”

- ✓ Develop a **federated network of computational facilities and services**, software tools and advice on policies and practices of research data management,
- ✓ Develop **Data Science and AI Institute** spanning and embedded at African institutions,
- ✓ Promote **collaboration on African priority application programmes** – ranging from health, biodiversity, disaster risk reduction, agriculture and open innovation resilient cities etc.,
- ✓ Create a **Network for Education and Skills in data and information**,
- ✓ Create a **Network for Open Science Access and Dialogue**

AOSP Strategy & Implementation Imperatives:

- Governance
- Platform Management
- Stakeholder Engagement
- Resource Mobilisation
- Operations
- Enabling Activities
- Application Activities
- Monitoring & Evaluation Framework

AOSP consists of several regional nodes

Role of nodes:

- ✓ Programme delivery and implementation
- ✓ Coordination
- ✓ Policy
- ✓ Resource Mobilisation
- ✓ Education and skills programmes
- ✓ Societal engagement , dialogue and open access

Community Development and Outreach ORCID Grant

AfricArXiv – pan-African Open Access portal will establish ORCID-facilitated multi-stakeholder consortia for efficient scholarly knowledge sharing from Africa, utilizing scholarly repository systems, each with a regional and research topic/discipline-specific focus. Also integrate and advocate for the adoption of other relevant persistent identifiers—ROR in particular—for African institutional reputation building, complementing the existing institutional infrastructure.

Policy Related Activities

- National Open Science Roadmaps - work been done in various countries across Africa at different stages
- Data Management Plan frameworks
- National repository for publications and data Open Science advocacy meetings and conducting an Open Science readiness assessment
 - ✓ Côte d'Ivoire, Ethiopia, Ghana, Lesotho, Mozambique, Nigeria, Somalia, Tanzania and Uganda

Activities

- Supporting Open Science Policy Development in the Continent
 - ✓ Ivory Coast
 - ✓ South Africa
 - ✓ Tanzania
 - ✓ North Africa

Open Science Activities with SGC

- SGC and Researcher continental and global visibility National
- Open repository for publications and data ✓ Depositing in repository with PIDs (DOI)
 - ✓ Participation in Data sharing using PIDs (DOI)
 - ✓ Create a SGC output sharing platform (Research data, Publication, resource documents, training, Communities of practice etc)
 - ✓ Training on all OS activities
- Developing Open Science (OA/OD) Policy and Implementation frameworks - Data Management Plan frameworks

Discussion

What can you do to encourage accountability throughout so many culturally diverse regions?

Give regional nodes freedom/flexibility in implementing what works best for their area

Is it sometimes condescending to fund research activities (e.g., paying article processing charges)?

Rather than just funding, think about collaborating together and include everyone in the research process.

Why are higher education institutions not enrolled in the effort?

They are currently being enrolled.

What is the role of libraries in the African open science forum?

It's not a platform, it's an initiative! Universities could be asked to involve libraries.

Key Takeaways

- The global north is where the most visible open science activities are conducted; we must consider ways to change this.
- Through the formulation of policies, community involvement, resource mobilisation, and the creation of an open science monitoring and reward structure, the African Open Science Platform is putting open science mechanisms in place in Africa.
- The cultures and languages in Africa are diverse. This calls for strategies that grant regions flexibility and autonomy.

Plenary Talk: Review Of The Week - What Has Been Learned?

Tim Smith (CERN)

Accelerating the Adoption of Open Science: A conference to discuss open science policy

- Policy makers, practitioners, promoters, ++
- Research Institutions, Universities, Government Agencies, Funding Agencies, and more!
- Here to: Develop / Refine / Align Open Science Policies

Shared Culture of NASA and CERN: Naturally Open

- **CERN:**
 - *Born in 1954*
 - *Convention: the results of its experimental and theoretical work shall be published or otherwise made generally available*
 - *Data: 0(500)PB opendata.cern.ch launched in 2014*
 - *Policy: 2020 Open Data Policy' 2022 Open Science Policy*
- **NASA**
 - *born in 1958*
 - *Charter: Provide for the widest practicable and appropriate dissemination of information concerning its activities and the results thereof*
 - *Data:0(100)PB data.nasa.gov started in 2014*
 - *Policy: 2021 Scientific Information Policy*

Day 1: Accelerating Open Science

Knowledge Production

- Moving away from science as a commodity (owned by commercial companies, rankings, monetisation)
 - Access to knowledge at cost; less-resourced are excluded
 - Owners determine future of openness and future restrictions
 - Patronizing strategies bestowed by the owner
 - With science in the logic of the market, we lose:
 - Institutional infrastructure, control and capacity on decision making, sustainability
- How can it be improved by open practices?
 - Research efficiency and productivity, quality, transparency, multilingualism
 - Exchange, foster new links, collaboratively rather than competitively
 - OS as a global enterprise
 - Not two track (open and closed); just one science. Not an add-on

Not Just for Science

- Not an end in itself, but a means to achieve science as a global public good
 - Cannot become a public good if public is not engaged
 - Think in terms of values in adopting OS, not just OS in itself
 - Quality and integrity, collective benefit
 - Increase accessibility of knowledge
- Increase inclusivity
 - Fulfill the human right of access to science Article 27

- Democratize the entire scientific process, not just the outputs
- Not just doing same things openly, but doing things differently, embrace new actors which also hold knowledge
- Equity is two way, not just to benefit the poor, but to engage everyone that holds knowledge
- Open Science or Scholarship
 - natural, social and human ... not semantics, same challenges but different means to achieve
 - “open work” rather than research

Change

- Socially disruptive transition
 - Eliminate historical inertias such as research assessment (individuals) and rankings (institutes)
- A behavior change movement, but two cultural elements interfere
 - Science is decentralized across institutions, funders, publishers. It is fundamentally a structural problem, not individual
 - The values are already intrinsic to the individuals, but not to the structures
- Change of all the actors to translate from the policy ... to the lab ... to the individual
 - Coordination problem - no one change will make it happen
 - Embracing bottom up - where there are needs
 - Think modularly, rather than single solutions, centralisation
 - Distributed as possible, interconnect where necessary

Policies

- Show commitment, build stability, enhance clarity, build engagement (of actors that will be affected), remove barriers
- Focus on the larger goals connected to open science practice; tackling of societal challenges
- Can be national or institutional; depends on context
- Can be by component (data, sw, access, science); w/something to federate these, a strategic framework
 - Can lead with any, but which you foreground sets tone (norms of open source)
- Address socio-technical aspects together coherently
- Private, public, individual interests. Need to be careful of unintended consequences
- Additionally:
 - A plan: How policy can translate into action on the ground
 - Infrastructures for the release of open science resources
 - An incentive structure that credits open science practices

Day 2: Open Data

Open?

- As open as possible as closed as necessary

- Not all public access data can be open, but all public access data should be FAIR
- Open isn't helping researchers
- Open is a misnomer
 - Don't talk about Open or FAIR data, instead RDM
- Managing data is in the researcher's self interest
 - To find and use again themselves
 - To work with collaborators when structured
- Commons are everywhere, institute, thematic, federated clouds, platforms, etc researcher in middle
 - Core element: interoperability and standards
- Open is not enough
 - Data is not enough
 - Workflow is the new data!

Context

- Additional assets that are needed to use the data
 - Content metadata
 - Provenance metadata
 - Contextual metadata
- Needs to be captured as the data is being recorded and analysed
- Accept the initial time it takes to do it properly
 - Employer that says "take the time to acquire and use skills to manage your data properly"
- Looking for culture change, making it easy to do, want to do it. Not monitoring them on compliance
- Don't worry about not good enough. Don't be afraid that could be better before release
- OS happens due to motivated individuals. Find them and work with them

Policies

- Research data management policy not open data policy
- Imposing a policy from outside only gets you enemies. Needs to be built from the inside
- Policy needs to speak the language of the practitioners
- Policies are agile: they need to be continuously updated and refined through feedback circles
- Address embargoes
- Use vague / specific language where necessary
- A policy is only as good as its implementation
 - Policy needs Infrastructure which needs resources (money, time, people)
 - Design tools to implement the policy together with researchers; Build "together" not "for"
- Practice
 - Give people resources and time to develop skills which are useful immediately / if leave academia

- Reward practices when looking at CVs and grants, taking all outputs as valuable contributions

Day 3: Open Source

Software is an Integral Part

- SW is essential to science, but we don't treat it as such!
 - Need it to collect, store, process, manage, simulate, analyse, visualise, disseminate
 - Need it to better understand results and increase their reproducibility
- SW is a tool, a research outcome, a research object
 - Access to the source code is essential!
 - Tools built by scientists for their science
- But SW isn't valued sufficiently:
 - Papers are not the only measure of intellectual contributions
- Nor taught accordingly
 - Computers are scientific instruments - teach scientists how to use them well
- Open Hardware has just as crucial a role to play!

Software is not just another Research Object

- Practices
 - Open-source practice showcases key cultural differences to traditional academic practice
- Objects
 - Publications are fire and forget, and accumulate dividends later, citations,
 - Scientific Software projects: (inverse!) an internal liability with recurring payments
- Credit
 - Black Hole discovery, did try to credit the entire chain, 23k people!
 - By package doesn't attribute importance
 - LoC doesn't measure contribution
- Avoid purely numerical indicators
 - Count quality software contributions
 - Establish intelligent and effective incentives

Open

- EULA ... Understand the nature of the world, using tools that you agree not to try to understand
- Open source is not antonym to commercial it is antonym to proprietary
- Open source is a change of paradigm to interacting with SW, not just *users*, but *decision makers*
 - Gives opportunity to bend SW to particular needs, to invest and improve
 - Not a liability. Proprietary you can sue and wait!

- When you use SW as infrastructure you are now a stakeholder and should support them!
- Embedded in a wider ecosystem of scientific tools no matter what discipline
- Support mutualised common infrastructures

Community

- Open source is more than code: notebooks, software, standards and protocols, community
- Without community open-source projects risk catastrophic success
- To run a community requires skills that are not taught; people are complicated and messy
- Scientists need support to produce open source
 - Provide financial, organizational and legal support
 - Governance and structure
 - Security and metrics
 - Business perspectives (knowing what to do with funding)

Policies

- No one size fits all, each Org needs to craft their own environment, but broad guidelines are useful
 - Guidelines on how to do good software development and how to contribute back
 - When to upstream, when to build business or build a community around
 - Best implemented through an OSPO
 - If not careful can get incompatible mandates of OSPO and tech transfer, so involve them
- OSPO
- Outwards and inward facing mission
 - Guidance and support: a place where can ask questions and get answers
 - Training and awareness
 - Justifying to hierarchy the value of time and effort invested
 - Identify what are you building on top of and how to contribute back to time, resources, money
 - Crucial in making sure that value is returned to the open-source community

Day 4: Reproduce, Reuse, Reward

Principles

- OS definitions include epistemic values (integrity) and societal (ethical)
 - Satisfying some objectives can be seen as failing others
- Codes of conduct (for research integrity) are not ready for open science
 - Concentrate on FFP, rather than citizen science, societal benefit, open collaboration
- Inclusivity and participatory ... can come at expense of ... scalability and sustainability

- Trust in research data/software is closely connected to the institution
- Institutions need to guarantee the reliability of research data!
- Institutions need to take responsibility for reproducibility!

Policies

- Dashboards can apply peer pressure for positive change (need exposure to participants only first)
- Offering awards for open data reuse, preregistration, null results - hooks for engagement
- Rewards
 - Alignment personal incentives and what is good for science
 - A very broad actor base (especially on the institutional level) is necessary to transform research assessment practices in academia
- Culture change has to happen by actions that make a difference to day-to-day research activity

Day 5: Towards Open Science

Governance

- Open science as enabler for participatory science and science democratization
- Open science in the context of the challenges that a specific region faces
- Social appropriation of science technology and innovation
 - Ancestral and traditional knowledge
- Creating and sustaining momentum
- Aligning incentives
- Making Open Science *required ... rewarding, normative, easy ... possible*